

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The article provides recommendations for teachers on using innovative approaches in working with students to develop logical and creative thinking in children, as well as solving non-standard problems in various fields of activity. Some didactic approaches to the formation of mathematical concepts and the development of logical thinking in preschool children are presented. The techniques and technologies for teaching children mathematics using educational and logical games are discussed, emphasizing the need for systematic preparation of children for mastering the school mathematics curriculum. The article also highlights the methods of introducing preschoolers to the Möbius strip technology. The possibilities of Möbius strip technology in the development of intellectual and personal qualities, spatial representations on a plane, visual-figurative thinking, attention, and logic are described.

Key words: conversation, symbolic modeling, game exercises, interactive games, solving mathematical problems, didactic games, problem-solving situations, experimentation, observation, collecting information about the studied object, reflection, preschool organization, development centers, mathematical concepts and competencies, play activities, preschool children, developmental environment.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada bolalarda mantiqiy va ijodiy fikrlashni shakllantirish, faoliyatning turli sohalarida nostandart muammolarni hal qilish bo'yicha talabalar bilan ishlashda innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanish bo'yicha o'qituvchilar uchun tavsiyalar berilgan. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda matematik tushunchalarni shakllantirish va mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning didaktik yondashuvlari keltirilgan. O'quv va mantiqiy o'yinlardan foydalangan holda bolalarga matematikani o'qitish texnikasi va texnologiyalari aniqlandi, bolalarni maktab matematika o'quv dasturini o'zlashtirishga tizimli ravishda tayyorlash zarurligi asoslandi. Maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni Möbius tasma texnologiyasi bilan tanishtirish usullarining xususiyatlari ochib berilgan. Möbius tasma texnologiyasining intellektual va shaxsiy fazilatlarini rivojlantirish, tekislikda fazoviy tasavvurlarni shakllantirish, vizual-majoziy fikrlash, e'tibor va mantiqni rivojlantirishdagi imkoniyatlari tasvirlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: suhbat, ramziy modellashtirish, o'yin mashqlari, interfaol o'yin, matematik masalalarni yechish, didaktik o'yinlar, muammoli vaziyatlarni yechish, eksperiment, kuzatish, o'rganilayotgan ob'ekt haqida ma'lumot to'plash, mulohaza yuritish, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasi, rivojlanish markazlari, matematik tushunchalar va qobiliyatlar, o'yin tadbirlari, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar, rivojlantiruvchi muhit.

Аннотация: В статье раскрываются некоторые рекомендации педагогам по использованию инновационных подходов в работе с учениками по формированию логического и творческого мышления у детей, решению нестандартных задач в различных сферах деятельности. Представлены некоторые дидактические подходы к формированию математических представлений и развитию логического мышления у детей дошкольного возраста. Раскрыты приемы и технологии обучения детей математике с использованием развивающих и логических игр, обоснована необходимость систематической подготовки детей к освоению школьной программы по математике. В статье раскрываются особенности методов ознакомления дошкольников с технологией ленты Мёбиуса. Описаны возможности технологии ленты Мёбиуса в развитии интеллектуальных и личностных качеств, формировании пространственных представлений на плоскости, наглядно-образного мышления, внимания и логики.

Ключевые слова: беседа, символическое моделирование, игровые упражнения, интерактивная игра, решение математических задач, дидактические игры, решение проблемных ситуаций, экспериментирование, наблюдение, сбор информации об изучаемом объекте, рефлексия, дошкольная организация, центры развития, математические понятия и компетенции, игровая деятельность, дети дошкольного возраста, развивающая среда.

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of developmental work is to provide children with the opportunity to independently choose how to apply their mental efforts, set personal goals, and find their own ways to achieve them¹. The introduction of state standards for preschool education has significantly transformed the role of teachers within the education system and, consequently, the responsibilities of educators. We believe that a teacher should transition from merely transferring knowledge to becoming a professional who teaches children how to acquire knowledge. This includes fostering cognitive interest, a desire for learning, and motivation to study through innovative technologies².

One of the key principles in organizing cognitive activities is stimulating a child's curiosity. Educational work should incorporate various didactic materials that engage children's interest. One such material is the Möbius strip. Children enjoy lessons where they actively participate in the learning process, as this encourages them to complete tasks willingly and enthusiastically. This interactive approach makes it easier for them to perform actions, draw simple conclusions, and formulate generalizations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An educational curriculum involves learning programs within or outside the classroom, activities, equipment, planning, timetables, subjects, and the evaluation process (McKimm, 2003)³. The curriculum does not only focus on learning experiences in school but also encompasses every moment in daily life, whether in a nursery, at home, or outside (Kernan, 2007). Robinson (2004) stated that specialists from the Early Childhood Unit of the National Children's Bureau, United Kingdom, believe that the curriculum for young children placed in care centers includes the following elements: all learning and development opportunities available to children; all activities, attitudes, and behaviors, whether planned or not, either encouraged or prohibited; methods for arranging the physical environment surrounding children, as well as the daily routines of both adults and children; the role of adults in organizing, leading, influencing, and participating in children's activities; and the involvement of parents in the aspects mentioned above⁴.

Preschool education is an early preparation for formal education that should attract children and instill a love for knowledge and schooling from an early stage (Ali & Mahamod, 2015)⁵. It is a crucial experience that provides useful, meaningful, and enjoyable learning, equipping children with skills, confidence, and a positive mindset in preparation for formal and lifelong education (Chin & Zakaria, 2015; Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008). Preschool education serves as a foundation before children enter school, making it the earliest formal education stage after home-based learning. Therefore, preschool teachers should possess extensive knowledge regarding early childhood education, including children's developmental aspects, teaching and learning strategies, preschool administration, and other related areas (Nasri, Halim, & Ghani, 2018; UNICEF, 2008)⁶. Preschool education programs introduce children to knowledge, skills, and values through practical and enjoyable learning experiences using a play-based approach. This method is flexible, dynamic, comprehensive, interactive, and engaging, emphasizing exploration and fostering curiosity among children (Samuelsson & Kaga, 2008).

Early mathematics education is essential as it lays the foundation for young children to understand advanced mathematical concepts in the future (Bakar, 2017). Acquiring early mathematics knowledge through direct and meaningful experiences in an enjoyable environment helps cultivate students' interest in learning mathematics (Ginsburg et al., 2008). Concepts such as pre-numbers, early numbers, number operations, measurements, shapes, time, and space should be taught in alignment with children's developmental stages, as they form important components of early mathematics education in preschools⁷.

1 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4646931?type=doc>

2 Beloshistaya A.V. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning matematik qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish. Maktabgacha ta'lim fakultetlari talabalari uchun ma'ruzalar kursi. – M.: VLADOS, 2003. – 400 b.

3 McKimm, J. (2003). O'quv dasturini loyihalash va rivojlantirish.

4 Children Early Mathematics Development Based on a Free Play Activity Roslinda Rosli, Teo Wei Lin Center of Innovation in Teaching and Learning, The National University of Malaysia (UKM), Bangi, Malaysia

5 Aliza Ali & Zamri Mahamod (2015). Development of Play-Based Instruction Module for Teaching Preschoolers' Language Skills. January 2015. AUSTRALIAN JOURNAL OF BASIC AND APPLIED SCIENCES 9(34):110-118

6 Children Early Mathematics Development Based on a Free Play Activity Roslinda Rosli, Teo Wei Lin Center of Innovation in Teaching and Learning, The National University of Malaysia (UKM), Bangi, Malaysia.

7 Bakar, K. A. (2017). Young Children's Representations of Addition in Problem Solving. Creative Education, 8, 2232-2242.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Movement along the midline of the shape surface from a fixed point leads back to the starting point, which is why the Möbius strip is one-sided. If a Möbius strip is made of rubber, no matter how it is twisted or stretched, it will retain its one-sided nature. The single-sidedness of the Möbius strip is a topological property that remains unchanged under homoeomorphic transformations. In 1861, the German mathematician August Ferdinand Möbius proposed the simplest way to create a one-sided surface. To construct a Möbius strip, one must take a narrow strip of paper, twist one end by 180 degrees, and then glue the edges together. This results in a unique geometric figure – the Möbius strip. The research problem focuses on the method of modeling gaming problem-practical situations as an effective approach to fostering learning motivation in children. The purpose of the study is to develop a methodology for utilizing experimental research activities involving the Möbius strip in the educational field of “Cognition” with senior preschool children. The hypothesis states that to generate interest in the final result, it is necessary to create a problem situation that encourages curiosity and engagement. The novelty of the research is that this development can be applied in working with senior preschool children (6–7 years old) as an advanced educational activity. It is also suitable for mathematical circles and extracurricular learning programs. According to modern educational standards, even senior preschoolers can distinguish between simple planar and spatial shapes. They are familiar with the concepts of internal and external surfaces of shapes. Modeling the Möbius strip under the teacher’s guidance is not a difficult task for preschool-aged children, making it a valuable tool for early mathematical and cognitive development.

In this case, it is important to organize the modeling process so that children can understand the characteristics of the Möbius strip as a one-sided surface. The educator begins by posing a question: Are all objects bilateral? To explore this concept, an experiment is proposed. A box without a top cover or lid is used, with a pinhole made in one of its side walls. The scenario imagines a spider inside the box at the pinhole and an ant outside at the same pinhole. The ant wants to visit the spider but cannot crawl through the pinhole, so it must navigate the box’s surfaces. Regardless of its path, it must cross over the box’s edge. If the edge is covered with Velcro, the ant cannot reach its destination. The children conclude that this happens because the box has two sides. The educator then asks for examples of other bilateral surfaces, and the children name objects such as a glass cylinder, a closed box (cube), a brick (parallelepiped), and a ball (sphere). This leads to the next problem: Is there a shape that has only one surface?

The children are given glue, a brush, and two similar strips of graph paper, each with a middle line drawn with a felt-tip pen. Under the teacher’s guidance, they create two models: one forming a cylindrical tape or “ring,” and the other forming a Möbius strip by twisting one end by half a turn before gluing the ends together. The teacher repeatedly pronounces the name of this new geometric shape while assisting the children in firmly gluing the strips. The next activity involves playing with the cylindrical tape and the Möbius strip. The teacher instructs the children to mark a point on the dotted line of the cylindrical tape, imagining an ant sitting there while a spider is on the opposite side. The ant cannot crawl through the hole to reach the spider without crossing over the edge. The children recognize that this happens because the tape has two sides and two ends. When the same activity is performed with the Möbius strip, they discover that the ant can reach the spider without crossing the edge by simply moving along the dotted line. The educator explains that this is because the Möbius strip has a unique property—it is one-sided.

Another game, “Write a Letter,” further explores this concept. The children are instructed to write a letter in a fairy language without lifting their pencil from the paper or crossing over the edge. They find that they cannot completely fill both sides of the cylindrical tape, as it has two distinct surfaces. However, when performing the same task on a Möbius strip, they realize that they can write across the entire strip without ever crossing an edge, reinforcing the idea that it has only one side.

If you make an incision along the midline of a Möbius strip, instead of obtaining two separate loops, you will get a single, longer strip with twice the number of twists. This experiment demonstrates the unique topological properties of the Möbius strip. If you then cut this resulting strip along its midline again, you will get two intertwined loops.

A related experiment involves drawing and cutting out a paper soldier, then placing it on a Möbius strip along the midline. As the soldier moves along the path, it will return to the starting point but with its orientation reversed. This demonstrates the non-orientable nature of the Möbius strip.

For future inventors, there is an engineering challenge involving a sewing machine’s gear belt, which is placed on two pulleys. When in use, one side of the belt touches the pulleys’ surfaces while the other does not, causing uneven wear and eventual slipping. To prolong the belt’s life, a practical solution is to design it in the shape of a Möbius strip by introducing a half-twist before connecting the ends. This ensures that both sides of the belt experience equal wear, effectively doubling its lifespan⁸.

8 Written samples of tasks on Möbius strip are given in appendix 4

In modern early education, children are introduced to Euclidean geometry, which primarily involves transformations such as shifting, mirroring (axial symmetry), compression, and stretching. The pinnacle of this approach is the study of set theory, in which shapes can be broken down into individual points and reassembled into new forms. According to Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget, children naturally perceive geometric properties in reverse order. They first understand the classification of objects by color and shape (set theory) or the distinction between open and closed loops (topology) before recognizing more complex geometric forms such as rectangles and hexagons (Euclidean geometry). Thus, introducing young children to the Möbius strip aligns well with their natural cognitive development⁹.

The proposed educational methodology is economical, using simple and accessible materials; dynamic, as it can be performed in just one or two lessons; innovative, as it introduces preschoolers to a new class of geometric shapes—one-sided surfaces; and comprehensive, as it is based on various teaching techniques that can be applied in group learning settings¹⁰.

The objective of introducing children to the Möbius strip is to familiarize them with this unique geometrical shape through hands-on activities and interactive games. The learning goals include reinforcing the understanding of quadrilateral shapes and their classification as rectangles, developing awareness of the one-sided nature of the Möbius strip, and enhancing logical reasoning skills. Materials needed include strips of paper and small objects such as toy insects, pencils, or pens.

The Möbius strip has been applied in various technical fields. Conveyor belts designed in a Möbius shape last longer because the entire surface wears evenly. In continuous tape recording, Möbius strips were historically used to double the recording time. Some researchers hypothesize that the DNA double-helix structure contains Möbius-like properties, which may contribute to the complexity of genetic information and biological aging. Magicians use the Möbius strip in tricks such as the “Afghan ribbon,” where cutting along the midline produces a single, longer loop with twice the number of twists instead of two separate strips. Many dot-matrix printers use Möbius-shaped ink ribbons to maximize efficiency. Some sharpening belts are also designed as Möbius strips to ensure even wear. The international recycling symbol is inspired by the Möbius strip, and its form has been incorporated into numerous artistic and architectural designs, ranging from traditional to highly innovative interpretations.

The Möbius strip is a fascinating geometric shape with profound implications in mathematics, engineering, and real-world applications. Its unique one-sided property makes it an excellent tool for teaching children about topology, logic, and creativity. By incorporating the Möbius strip into early childhood education, we can foster deeper mathematical intuition and problem-solving skills in young learners.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Reviewed trends help to shape logical and diagrammatic thinking regarding existing relationships, naturally integrating children into the world of both trivial and nontrivial logic, based on creative thinking. As a result, preschoolers develop the ability to understand communication patterns and the fundamental principles underlying scientific knowledge. While abstract concepts remain figurative for young learners, they actively grasp conditional algorithmic thinking schemes—a mental model.

It is important to remember that the content of mathematical development activities for children, regardless of the approach, must align with their age-specific characteristics and training requirements. These activities should facilitate further development, consider the possibilities offered by modern information technologies, and provide mechanisms for adaptation¹¹.

The forms and methods of instruction should be determined by the necessity of implementing humanistic principles, allowing children to explore the world through play and ensuring a harmonious integration of social and family education. This is achieved through self-oriented cooperation between adults and children in the organization of children’s activities.

The presented approach establishes the following key perspective for teachers: it encourages allowing children to explore their own ways of solving educational problems, following their individual learning styles. This approach preserves the unique, multi-level, and diverse nature of preschoolers’ understanding of mathematics as a field of knowledge.

This perspective directs teachers toward developing a strong mathematical foundation based on set theory, employing subtle yet effective methods and techniques that enhance mathematical comprehension among all subjects involved in the learning process.

9 Moylett, H., & Stewart, N. (2012). *Development Matters in the Early Years Foundation Stage*. London: Early Education.

10 Djanpeisova G.E. and others. Innovative approaches in the education and development of preschool children/ *Psychology and Education* (2021) 58(2): 1205-1210 issn: 00333077. 1205-1210 p.

11 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1871187122001134>

An analysis of existing preschool and primary school programs in the field of mathematical development, along with our long-term observations and experimental research, highlights the effectiveness of integrating a set-theoretic approach with the study of scalar quantities and their properties.

Effective approaches follow the logical sequence: "Set → Quantity → Number → Relationship." This sequence is an inherent part of modern trends in mathematical child development and is also discussed in this guide.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To ensure the effectiveness of mathematics learning, teachers must recognize and accommodate the diverse cultural backgrounds and needs of various groups of children. Managing a classroom requires the ability to multitask, make crucial decisions instantly, and adapt flexibly to unexpected changes. Mathematics is an abstract and complex subject; therefore, fostering meaningful learning through play-based activities should be a key focus in the preschool curriculum. Play-based approaches not only nurture children's interest in mathematics but also positively shape their attitudes toward the subject. Teachers should remain professional and avoid personal emotions during interactions with young learners, as early childhood education presents unique challenges in organizing and implementing various play activities. Ultimately, teachers must prioritize their professional development and continuously strive for improvement, as they serve as role models for children and significantly influence their learning experiences.

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